

Study in Nitrogen Mustards, Part III Synthesis of Some 2-alkyl-3-aryl-4 (3H)-quinazolinone Derivatives with Nitrogen Mustard Moiety as Possible Anti-tumour Agents

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A number of 2-alkyl-3-aryl-derivatives of 4(3H)-quinazolinone have been synthesised. The different compounds contain one or more, mono or bifunctional mustard grouping, attached to the heterocyclic nucleus through an enzymetically hydrolyzable linkage. The newly synthesised compounds have been studied for their pharmacological action as antitumor agents.

As a part of our work, another group of fifty compounds belonging to the quinazolinone series, containing one or more nitrogen mustard groups, were prepared and studied for their pharmacological action. One of the very basic reasons for the study of these nitrogen mustards was based on the observation that related carrier molecules (for example, antimalarial drugs¹), exhibited preferential localisation in different systems and tissues depending upon the chemical structure of the heterocyclic molecule. A large number of a variety of substituted quinoline and acridine carrier derivatives, synthesised by Pack *et al*² and Creech *et al*³ gave an idea that these compounds might permit the accumulation of the mustard moiety in specific tissues and presumably also in the existing tumors of these tissues. It was also thought that the exceptionally high activities of these mustard derivatives might be detrimental to the idea of greater effectiveness, since any enhanced degree of activity displayed during the transport of drug to the affected area would tend to limit the localisation of effective compound⁴. We considered it of interest to incorporate these structural features in a fused heterocyclic system as 2-aminoalkyl and 3-substituted arylamino-quinazolinones.

The various substituted quinazolinone derivatives were synthesised according to the scheme as shown, by condensing equimolar quantities of methyl-*o*-N, N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl) aminoacylamidobenzoates with the substituted arylamines in the presence of phosphorous trichloride in dry toluene according to the method of Mewada *et al*⁵. PCl_3 was used as binding material for the closure of the ring system.

The various steps involved in the syntheses are as follows: methyl-anthranilate was treated with chloroacyl chlorides to get methyl-*o*-chloro-acylamido-benzoate derivatives, which were further condensed with diethanolamine in absolute alcohol to obtain methyl-*o*-N,N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl) aminoacylamido-benzoates. The various substituted aryl amines used for condensation reactions are as reported in our previous paper.⁶ The different hydrazides, sulphonamides and phenylenediamine derivatives were prepared according to Ishidate *et al*⁷, Benn *et al*⁸ and Tsou *et al*⁹. The substituted quiazolones were further treated with thionyl chloride in dry chloroform, according to the method of Mann,¹⁰ to get the desired mustard moiety. The different compounds are reported in Tables 1-4.

The case of hydrazides, the ring closure was observed by refluxing the substituted benzoates with bis(2-hydroxyethyl) hydrazine in absolute alcohol, according to the method of Bhargava *et al*¹¹. The 2-substituted alkyl 3-bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino-4-(3H)-quinazolinone was then further treated with thionyl chloride or phosphorous tribromide, to get the required mustard derivatives.

It will be worth mentioning that the compounds were prepared with the idea of studying the effect of

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enzymetically hydrolyzable linkage of the side chain between the heterocyclic nucleus and the mono- or bifunctional nitrogen mustard grouping *in situ*. The compounds have shown reduced activity in various biological test systems *in vitro* and on subcutaneous administration, the monofunctional compounds were more toxic than the bifunctional analogs. None of the monofunctional compounds produced leucopenia at the LD₅₀ does level, which contrasts with the marked leucopenia produced by the bifunctional compounds when tested against lymphoid leukemia L₁₂₁₀. The compounds are, in general, of low toxicity and some compounds are nontoxic even at high doses. The newly synthesised compounds have been screened for their biological evaluations as antimicrobial and antifertility agents and the results of their pharmacological studies shall be submitted later on. A full length paper on their anticancer activity is appearing shortly.

The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, i.r. spectroscopy and chemical studies.

Experimental

All melting points were determined by using Gallen-kamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

Methyl-o-chloroacetamido-benzoate :

Chloroacetyl chloride (11.0 g., 0.1 mole) taken in dry benzene (30 ml) was gradually added to methyl-anthranilate (15.1 g, 0.1 mole) in dry benzene (50 ml). The mixture was heated on a steam bath under reflux for 4 hr. Benzene was then distilled off and the residual mass was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The solid mass obtained was washed with water and crystallised from benzene in white crystalline needles (60%), m.p. 79-80°. Found, N, 6.21 ; Cl, 15.79. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₀O₃NCl, N, 6.16 ; Cl, 15.60%.

Methyl-o-N, N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl)aminoacetamido-benzoate :

A mixture of methyl-o-chloroacetamido-benzoate (13.65 g., 0.1 mole) and diethanolamine (12.60 g., 0.1 mole) was refluxed together on a steam bath for five hours, in abs. alcohol. Excess of alcohol was removed by distillation and the residual mass was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid. It was filtered and the filtrate was made alkaline with ammonia solution. The base was collected, washed with water and crystallised from minimum amount of alcohol in long needles (50%), m.p. 138-139°.

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	n	X	Y	Y'	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen (%)	
								Found	Calcd.
1.	1	OH	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) ₂	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	159-160	51	10.85	11.00
2.	1	OH	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	172-173	72	10.17	10.26
3.	1	OH	-CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ Br	Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ BrCl	229-230	40	10.41	10.60
4.	1	OCH ₃	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) ₂	Cl	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	148-149	50	10.50	10.70
5.	1	OCH ₃	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	230-231	90	9.88	10.00
6.	1	OCH ₃	-CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	169-170	48	11.55	11.70
7.	1	OCH ₃	-CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ Br	Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ BrCl ₂	248-249	75	10.20	10.35
8.	1	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) ₂	Cl	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	144-145	73	10.33	10.46
9.	1	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	229-230	65	9.66	9.80
10.	1	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Br) ₂	Cl	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ Br ₂ Cl ₂	262-263	60	8.32	8.47
11.	1	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	163-164	73	11.19	11.40
12.	1	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₃	253-254	80	10.90	11.00
13.	1	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ Br	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ BrCl ₃	246-247	80	10.00	10.10
14.	0	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	-H	Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	162-163	45	10.72	10.85
15.	2	OH	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) ₂	Cl	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	174-176	75	10.52	10.71
16.	2	OH	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ ·2HCl	Cl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₆	206-207	70	9.82	10.00
17.	2	OH	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Br) ₂	Cl	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂ Br ₂	249-250	75	8.56	8.63
18.	2	OCH ₃	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ ·2HCl	Cl	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₆	238-240	60	9.60	9.75
19.	2	OCH ₃	-CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ Br	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ BrCl ₂	192-194	46	10.00	10.09
20.	2	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) ₂	Cl	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	160-161	54	9.94	10.16
21.	2	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	236-237	70	9.44	9.55
22.	2	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Br) ₂	Cl	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ Br ₂ Cl ₂	257-258	60		
23.	2	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	Cl	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₃	188-188	75	10.53	10.70
24.	2	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ Br	Cl	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ BrCl ₃	203-204	70	9.67	9.85
25.	0	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ - H	-H	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	159-161	48	10.38	10.56

Solvent for crystallisation : Ethyl alcohol ; Methyl alcohol-ether mixture.

Additional analyses were also performed for compounds 9, 12 and 22 (C, H, Cl) and the results were within ±0.4% of their calculated values.

2-N, N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl)aminomethyl-3-[3'-N, N-bis(2-chloroethyl)aminomethyl-4'-hydroxy]phenyl-4-(3H)-quinazolinone :

Methyl-o-[N, N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl) aminoaceta-mido]-benzoate (3.23 g, 0.01 mole) and 3-N, N-bis(2-chloroethyl) aminoethyl-4-hydroxyaniline (2.89 g, 0.01 mole) were refluxed together in the presence of phosphorous trichloride (1.3 ml.) in dry toluene (125 ml) according to the method of Mewada *et al*⁵. The base was crystallised from methyl alcohol in light yellow crystals (60%), m.p. 159-160°.

2-N, N-Bis(2-chloroethyl)aminomethyl-3-[3'-N, N-bis(2-chloroethyl)aminomethyl-4'-hydroxy]phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone :

2-N, N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) aminomethyl-3-[3'-N, N-bis(2-chloroethyl)aminomethyl-4'-hydroxy]-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (2.4 g) dissolved in dry chloroform (15 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred solution of thionyl chloride (10 ml) in dry chloroform taken in a 100 ml three neck round bottomed flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer, a condenser and a dropping funnel. The addition was completed in half an hour and the mixture was

further stirred for half an hour at room temp. The mixture was refluxed on steam bath for further 15 min. Excess of chloroform was removed and the last traces were removed under reduced pressure. The residual mass was dissolved in water and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The base was filtered, washed with ice cold water and crystallised from alcohol-ether mixture in yellow lumps (57%), m.p. 172-173°.

Similarly other compounds of this series were prepared.

Methyl-o-(α -chloropropionamido)-benzoate :

α -Chloropropionyl chloride was treated with methyl-anthranilate in equimolar ratios in dry benzene by the usual method described earlier. The product was crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 121-114°.

Methyl-o-[α -N, B-bis(2-hydroxyethyl)aminopropionamido]-benzoate :

A mixture of methyl-o-(α -chloropropionamido)-benzoate (0.5 mole) and diethanolamine (0.2 mole) were refluxed together in absolute alcohol by the

TABLE-2

Sl. No.	n	Z	Y'	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen (%)	
							Found	Calcd.
1.	1	-CH ₂ CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH)	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	152-153	56	12.58	13.00
2.	1	-CH ₂ CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ OCl ₄	190-191	80	11.80	11.96
3.	1	-CH ₂ CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Br) ₂	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O.Br ₂ Cl ₂	214-216	60	9.92	10.05
4.	1	-SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ Cl ₄ S	110-112	48	9.44	9.65
5.	2	-SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ Cl ₄ S	84-85	52	9.81	9.73
6.	2	-CH ₂ CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) ₂	Cl	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ Cl ₂	156-157	57	12.40	12.58
7.	2	-CH ₂ CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O.Cl ₄	197-198	60	11.51	11.62

TABLE-8

Sl. No.	X	Y	Y'	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen (%)	
							Found	Calcd.
1.	OH	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ Cl ₄	199-200	60	9.82	10.00
2.	OCH ₃	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ Cl ₄	182-188	52	9.58	9.78
3.	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃ Cl ₄	169-171	49	9.41	9.52
4.	OCH ₃	-CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Br) ₂	Cl	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ Br ₂ Cl ₂	211-212	48	8.27	8.44
5.	OCH ₃	-CH ₂ NH.CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ Cl ₂	179-180	48	10.23	10.34
6.	OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ NH.CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	Cl	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₃ Br.Cl ₂	216-217	50	9.71	9.82
7.	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ - H	-CH ₂ NH.CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O.Cl ₄	160-161	55	10.50	10.56

TABLE-4

Sl. No.	Z	Y'	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen (%)	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	-CH ₂ CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O.Cl ₄	214-216	45	11.50	11.62
2.	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O.Cl ₄	229-230	60	12.21	12.33
3.	-SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ Cl ₄ S	137-138	48	9.32	9.42

Solvent for crystallisation : Ethyl alcohol , Aqueous alcohol , Methanol.

usual method. The base was crystallised from alcohol in white fluffy needles (53%), m.p. 145-147°.

The other compounds similarly prepared and are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Methyl-o-(β-chloropropionamido)-benzoate :

β-Chloropropionyl chloride (0.1 mole) was treated with methyl-anthranilate (0.1 mole) in dry benzene by the previously described method. The product was crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 123-125°.

Methyl-o-[β-N,N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl)aminopropionamido]-benzoate :

A mixture of methyl-o-(β-chloropropionamido)-benzoate (0.5 mole) and diethanolamine (0.2 mole) were refluxed together in abs. alcohol by the method detailed before. The product was crystallised from the minimum amount of ethanol in white lumps, m.p. 153-154°.

2-[N,N-Bis(2-chloroethyl)aminoethyl(-β)]-3-aryl-4-(3H)quinazolinones :

The different compounds of this series were prepared by condensing equimolar amounts of methyl-o-[β-N,N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl)aminopropionamido]-benzoate with the substituted aryl amine in the presence of phosphorous trichloride in dry toluene as explained earlier. The products were crystallised from the suitable solvents.

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